

NOTES

TABLE 1

No. of compounds	n as in 1	C		H		N		M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula
		Reqd. %	Found %	Reqd. %	Found %	Reqd. %	Found %			
1.	2	45.7	45.5	3.8	3.9	20.0	20.2	274	64	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂
2.	3	47.0	47.2	4.1	4.4	19.3	19.0	122	60	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂
3.	4	48.2	48.5	4.4	4.2	18.7	18.4	231	50	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂
4.	5	49.3	49.1	4.7	4.4	18.2	18.3	228	63	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂
5.	6	50.4	50.7	5.0	4.9	17.6	17.3	265	65	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂
6.	7	51.4	51.6	5.3	5.1	17.1	16.8	132	46	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂
7.	8	52.3	52.5	5.5	5.6	16.6	16.3	307-308(d)	52	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂
8.	9	53.2	53.5	5.7	5.9	16.2	15.9	109	43	C ₂₃ H ₃₀ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂
9.	10	54.1	54.3	6.0	5.9	15.8	15.9	322(d)	70	C ₂₄ H ₃₂ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂
10.	12	55.7	55.8	6.4	6.2	15.0	14.9	210	75	C ₂₆ H ₃₆ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂

All the melting points are uncorrected and the compounds were recrystallised from water. (d) = decomposed.

TABLE 2

Test compound	n as in 1	No. of animals	Initial blood sugar (mg/100 ml)	Blood sugar (mg/100 ml) level after	
				1 hr	3 hr
Control	x	3	101.94 ± 5.2*	99.86 ± 4.5	98.68 ± 5.2
1	2	3	100.79 ± 0.86	88.71 ± 2.25	69.02 ± 1.46
2	3	3	93.75 ± 1.63	75.08 ± 1.46	73.32 ± 1.40
3	6	3	93.22 ± 2.42	94.76 ± 2.21	76.25 ± 9.65
4	7	3	92.59 ± 0.74	72.78 ± 10.68	76.79 ± 7.24
5	8	3	95.09 ± 2.50	91.38 ± 3.19	77.01 ± 4.51
6	9	3	85.89 ± 2.66	80.11 ± 0.14	64.67 ± 12.07
7	10	3	94.77 ± 0.84	82.58 ± 6.30	65.70 ± 6.36
8	12	3	95.54 ± 8.37	103.48 ± 2.50	67.73 ± 5.42
Tolbutamide	—	5	87.12 ± 14.00	69.95 ± 13.12	52.36 ± 15.90

* Mean ± Standard error.

150-200 g fasted for 18 hr. (water was allowed ad. lib.).

The blood sugar was determined by collection of blood from the tail of the rats and determined by the method of Folin and Wu⁹.

A suspension of 250 mg/kg of the test compounds in gum acacia was administered orally to ten groups of rats. The blood sugar was determined after 1 and 3 hr. All of the test drugs and the reference drug, tolbutamide were administered at 250 mg/kg. Preliminary results are reported in Table 2.

It may be noted that compounds with n = 2, 10 and 12 (as in 1) are showing high activity under conditions at which tolbutamide is known to exhibit hypoglycemic activity.

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Thermal Synthesis of Glycozoline

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RECENTLY diphenylamine (I) has been shown to cyclise to carbazole¹ (II) under thermal condition at a temperature of 350° in presence of trace amounts of iodine as catalyst. The method was extended to the synthesis of glycozolidine¹, C₁₅H₁₅NO₂ (III), m.p. 160°-62°, a carbazole alkaloid of *Glycosmis pentaphylla*. We now report a new synthesis of glycozoline^{2,3}, C₁₄H₁₃NO (IV) m.p. 181°-82°, a

carbazole alkaloid of the same plant using the above thermal method of synthesis.

The starting diphenylamine, 4'-methoxy-4-methyl-diphenylamine (V), m.p. 122°-23°, was synthesised from *p*-toluidine hydrochloride and *p*-anisidine. The diphenylamine derivative was then heated in a sealed tube at 350° in presence of iodine for 3 hr. After the reaction was complete, the product was taken up in benzene and chromatographed over alumina. From the reaction mixture a compound m.p. 181°-82° was obtained which was found to be identical with natural glycozoline (IV) (i.r., u.v., m.m.p.).

- I, $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = H$
 V, $R_1 = H$; $R_2 = CH_3$; $R_3 = OCH_3$
 II, $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = H$
 III, $R_1 = R_3 = OCH_3$; $R_2 = CH_3$
 IV, $R_1 = H$; $R_2 = CH_3$; $R_3 = OCH_3$

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Petroleum ether had the boiling point 60°-80° unless otherwise mentioned. For chromatography (tlc and column) silica gel supplied by Gouri Chemical, Calcutta and alumina of M/s. Saiabhai Merck, India were used.

4'-Methoxy-4-methyl diphenylamine (V) :

p-Toluidine hydrochloride (500 mg) was mixed with *p*-anisidine (1 g) and heated at 270° for 4 hr. After the reaction the product was taken up in ethyl acetate, it was washed with 1% HCl and then with water and dried over anh. Na_2SO_4 . It was then filtered, the solvent distilled and the residue taken in benzene and chromatographed over alumina. The petroleum ether benzene (1 : 1) eluent furnished (V), in a crystalline form, m.p. 122°-23°. Yield 200 mg. [Found : C, 78.80; H, 7.0; N, 6.55%; requires C, 78.94; H, 7.09; N, 6.57%] λ_{max}^{EtOH} 272, 263, 232 nm with $\log \epsilon$ 4.58, 4.60, 4.32; ν_{max}^{NaCl} 3450, 1620, 1520, 1470, 1300 cm^{-1} .

Glycozoline (IV) :

Diphenylamine (V; 100 mg) was heated in a sealed tube at 350° in presence of a trace amount of iodine for 3 hr. After this, the reaction product was taken in benzene and chromatographed over alumina. The benzene eluent furnished a solid which melted at 181° and was identical with natural glycozoline (ur, ir, mmp). Yield 20 mg.

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Formation Constants and Thermodynamic Study of Tl(I)-3-Nitro-Salicylates

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THE formation constants of Tl(I)-3NSA have been determined *pH*-metrically, employing half-integral method (HI), described by Irving and Rossotti¹. Refined values of formation constants are then obtained by linear-plot (LP), point-wise calculation (PC) and least square (LS) methods at three different temperatures, viz., 30°, 35° and 40°. The thermodynamic parameters, ΔF , ΔH , and ΔS , have also been calculated.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of Analar B.D.H. grade.

Polymetron model CL-41 *pH*-meter was used for *pH*-metric titrations conducted at 30°, 35° and 40°. Measurements were made with an accuracy of ± 0.05 *pH* unit and the reproducibility of the readings was of the same order. The *pH*-meter was calibrated using Cambridge buffer tablets of *pH* 4.01 and 9.11.

pH-Metric titrations of the solutions of (i) free $HClO_4$, (ii) free $HClO_4 + 3\text{-NSA}$ and (iii) free $HClO_4 + 3\text{-NSA} + Tl(I)$ were performed in 50% (v/v) aqueous-ethanol medium against standard NaOH solution while maintaining the ionic strength at 0.1M ($NaClO_4$).

The experimental set up and the method of calculation is the same as described earlier²⁻⁴.

Results and Discussion

The Irving-Rossotti expression¹ was used for the calculations of $\bar{n}$ and *p*(L). The proton-ligand formation constants of 3-NSA, as reported earlier⁵, under the same experimental conditions, were used for the calculation of *p*(L). In calculating $\bar{n}$ and *p*(L) the concentrations were corrected for the changes in volume as a result of addition of alkali during titration. A series of values of $\bar{n}$ and *p*(L) corresponding to different B-values (*pH*-meter reading) were calculated and formation curves obtained by plotting $\bar{n}$ versus *p*(L) (Fig. 1). The $\bar{n}$ values never exceed 1.7 indicating thereby, the formation of only 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes. The values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were calculated by half-integral method (HI) making use of formation curves. The values of *p*(L) at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and 1.5 correspond to the values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ respectively. Refined values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were also obtained using afore

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